

TRENDS IN THE ECONOMIC DIPLOMACY OF THE 21ST CENTURY

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Abstract: *In recent decades we have witnessed a considerable change in the power balance of global economic diplomacy. While in the past, the state undisputedly dominated the diplomatic arena, recently new actors from the field of civil society have entered this space, including supranational bodies and businesses and economic entrepreneurs, who have gained power and influence on decision-making processes. In a reality where globalization creates great interdependence between countries on a variety of issues, such as climate change, security issues and fighting terrorism, this change has a dramatic effect on the diplomatic field.*

Key words: *Economic Diplomacy; International Relations; Globalization.*

TENDINȚE ÎN DIPLOMAȚIA ECONOMICĂ A SECOLULUI XXI

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Rezumat: *În ultimele decenii am fost martori la o schimbare considerabilă a balanței de putere a diplomației economice globale. În timp ce în trecut statul domina incontestabil arena diplomatică, recent în acest spațiu au intrat noi actori din domeniul societății civile, inclusiv organismele supranaționale și întreprinderile și antreprenorii economici, care au câștigat putere și influență asupra proceselor decizionale. Într-o realitate în care globalizarea creează o mare interdependență între țări cu privire la o varietate de probleme, precum schimbările climatice, problemele de securitate și combaterea terorismului, această schimbare are un efect dramatic asupra domeniului diplomatic.*

Cuvinte cheie: *diplomație economică; relații internaționale; globalizarea; politica economică națională.*

In recent decades we have witnessed a considerable change in the power balance of global economic diplomacy. While in the past, the state undisputedly dominated the diplomatic arena, recently new actors from the field of civil society have entered this space, including supranational bodies and businesses and economic entrepreneurs, who have gained power and influence on decision-making processes. Economic national diplomacy had interaction with everything related international relations between countries.

Traditional diplomacy, designed in the 17th century, remained almost unchanged until the 20th century. After the Second World War, the concept of "democratic diplomacy" gradually developed, and it seems that it was fully realized in the last decades. This process has gradually led to a change in the way diplomacy works - from a relatively closed diplomacy focused on embassies, to a more open diplomacy that operates for example in conventions and through international agreements (such as the Kyoto and Seattle agreements), in which an increasing number of civil society organizations (NGOs) participate seeking to influence the agenda and making decisions. To illustrate, in 1946 only 41 civil society organizations were recognized within the UN as observers and invited to the international discussions, in 1992 the number increased to 3,000, and in 2014 it had already reached 4,000. Social economy organizations have managed to develop "civil diplomacy" characterized by three main features:

A. The organizations provide valuable information from the field, the importance of which sometimes exceeds the importance of information provided by the diplomats and the foreign service;

B. The organizations play a "watchdog" role before, during and after diplomatic negotiation processes;

C. The organizations can harness celebrities from various fields, and thus they can attribute even more weight to their positions in the eyes of the public than the positions of institutionalized government diplomacy;

The strengthening of economic-civil society's power requires a deep change in the way traditional-national diplomacy's works. However, the required change in the field of economic policy is complex in light of the civil society organizations' degree of legitimacy and their support base. Sometimes there is no correlation between the extent of their influence on t decision-making processes and the extent of public support for the principles they promote. In some areas there is extensive activity of economic civil society organizations, while in others the activity is limited. Nevertheless, a change in modern diplomacy is already taking place in several countries around the world, and in certain areas in Israel as well. An example of this is the cooperation forged between the Ministry of Foreign Affairs,

Ministry of Environmental Protection and Israeli environmental quality organizations to consolidate the position of the State of Israel in the drafting of the Rio+20 conference document for sustainable development.

In areas such as environmental quality and human rights, civil society's growing influence on the global agenda creates increasing pressure on decision makers at the national and international level. The growing influence of civil society has also led to establishing the legitimacy of cooperation between diplomacy and the private sector. In many cases this is manifested in tri-sector cooperation - governments, civil society organizations and businesses - and in the creation of *Private Public Partnerships* (PPP). The cooperation between diplomacy and the business sector achieves two complementary goals:

1. Increasing the socio-public activities of the Ministry of Foreign Affairs in the destination country;
2. Contribution to strengthening the economy in the country of origin.

An example of the implementation of the contribution of the economic civil societies. To illustrate, the American State Department **explicitly defines an economic foreign policy whose goals are: promoting American businesses abroad and creating jobs for American citizens, encouraging investments in the United States, and creating conditions for fair competition for American businesses abroad.** The Office of Global Partnerships, subordinate to the US Secretary of State, promotes partnerships in the Ministry of Foreign Affairs and around the world on the assumption that the main global challenges: climate change, poverty, terrorism, disease, insecurity and inequality are too complex and expensive for one government or a single organization. Forming the solutions requires innovation, initiative and cooperation between sectors. One of the prominent ways of working is forming partnerships with various entities, including large companies, start-up companies, civil society organizations, philanthropic foundations, academic institutions, religious organizations, research institutes and citizen groups, and leveraging business resources to solve the burning problems on the agenda, including through contribution to the community.

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